

Literature review: how do established models of mentoring relate to academic mentoring practice in the African context?

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Introduction and definitions

The role of academic mentoring in Africa has received more attention from researchers and practitioners in recent years, due to the growing research ecosystem on the continent (Nangami et al., 2014; Somefun and Adebayo, 2021), and the growth in international development projects and global health initiatives, which feature mentoring as a key component of capacity building and training initiatives (Lescano and Cohen, 2019). However, confusion exists over the definition and function of mentoring in academia, and the applicability of Global North models to the African context. This literature review looks at recent research on this phenomenon, how established theoretical models of mentoring relate to mentoring in practice, particularly in Africa, and what further research is needed for a deeper understanding of contemporary academic mentoring in an African context.

Mentoring has a complex history and an ever-evolving definitional terrain in different professional environments (Mullen and Klimaitis, 2019). However, Kram's (1985) definition provided a foundational benchmark, describing mentoring as a relationship between a more senior or experienced person and a junior person based around two functions – advice or modelling about career development, and personal and psychosocial support. More recently,

Lancer, Clutterbuck and Megginson (2016) noted that mentoring has evolved into two main branches: a 'sponsorship' model of mentoring, which is a US-inspired, hierarchical, directive model where the mentor sponsors or champions for the protégé, leaning on their authority and experience to provide hands-on advice in a one-way learning transaction; and a more European 'developmental model' which values both parties, and where the mentor helps the mentee to think for themselves, grow in self-efficacy and focus on the quality of the mentee's thinking. The latter model finds more favour in mentoring literature, for example Bozeman and Feeney (2007)'s holistic definition of the "...informal transmission of knowledge, social capital, and psychosocial support ... between a person who is perceived to have greater relevant knowledge, wisdom, or experience (the mentor) and a person who is perceived to have less (the protégé)". Clutterbuck (2014) goes further to describe a less directive two-way relationship based around "listening with empathy, sharing experience (usually mutually), professional friendship, [and] developing insight through reflection".

Functions of academic mentoring

A wealth of research has been conducted on mentoring in academic contexts, and particularly in the field of medicine, but Sambunjak et al., (2006)'s review discovered a remaining 'conceptual confusion' in the literature (Sambunjak et al., 2010), due to poor quality, frequent self-reported data, and a lack of detail and clear definitions of mentoring. Mentoring is commonly confused with other 'helping' roles such as coaching, training, and particularly research supervision (Sambunjak and Marusic, 2009). Additionally, many research findings are restricted to lists of descriptive statistics on surveys of participants in formal programmes (Burke and McKeen, 1997, p.44).

However, Sambunjak et al., (2010)'s later review documented qualitative research, mostly using thematic analysis or grounded theory approaches which demonstrates how mentoring differs from other professional support roles through a unique broadness of support – a 'uniquely encompassing relationship'. Nevertheless, there are still under-researched relational outcomes of mentoring such as personal growth, interdependence and connectedness (Sambunjak et al., 2010).

Qualitative research suggests that academic mentees appreciate elements of both developmental and sponsorship models. Developmental mentoring can be seen in support such as helping socialisation into academic culture (Rheineck and Roland, 2011), or aiding resilience and transition into independence as a researcher or practitioner (Brown et al., 2009; Sawatsky et al., 2016). Effective mentors also enhance self-belief (Schriever and Grainger, 2019), support emotional demands (Zentgraf, 2020) and build relationship skills through empathy and positive regard (Brown et al., 2009).

However, academic mentoring is also expected to cover training of practical skills (Zentgraf, 2020), inspire good research methods and scholarly values (Brown et al., 2009), and build technical skills such as research writing to increase publications (Schriever and Grainger, 2019). Additionally, some view sponsorship, protection and promotion of visibility as an essential part of the mentoring dyad (Sambunjak and Marusic, 2009), for example by providing access to networks (Zentgraf, 2020), career development through helping to 'open doors', or taking the mentee 'under their wing' (Jackson, 2003).

Hierarchy is important in this support – many mentees hope that their mentor has "a well-established position within the academic community" (Sambunjak and Marusic, 2009), or has academic 'clout' (Jackson, 2003).

These different manifestations of the key mentoring interventions along

developmental and sponsorship lines also relate to the distinction between directive (expert knowledge sharing) and non-directive support (focus on the mentee's thinking and reflection) – a major area of unresolved debate in the theoretical coaching and mentoring literature (Garvey, 2018, p.400).

The African context

Research on the African academic mentoring context is much more sparse, a fact lamented by Sambunjak et al., (2010), whose review was based entirely on the US context. A number of useful studies using qualitative analysis (mostly mixed methods and thematic analysis) have focused on African institutions (e.g. Nakanjako et al., 2011; Ssemata et al., 2017; Nwankwo, 2017; Phiri, 2019; and Owusu-Agyeman, 2022); as well as broader studies on the African mentoring landscape (Lescano et al., 2019; Oppong, 2022; Somefun and Adebayo, 2019). However, a significant proportion of the contemporary literature contextualises mentoring in global health leadership (Rodriguez et al., 2021; Rosser et al., 2020) and other capacity development programmes, (Cole et al., 2016; Nangami et al., 2014; Ngongalah et al., 2021) as well as the evaluation and training of mentors in the Global South (Chi and Belizan, 2019; Gandhi et al., 2019). This research is a mixture of project reports and evaluations as well as qualitative analysis.

In comparison with the Global North, African research culture tends to be more hierarchical, more accepting of seniority, and discourages challenge and critical thinking (Lescano et al., 2019; Cohen, 2019; Bennett and Paina, 2013), due to a “high power distance culture” (Clutterbuck, 2007, p.646). Additionally, Africa lacks the research mentoring culture that the US and Europe

have (Ghandi et al., 2019; Somefun and Adebayo, 2021), based on their stronger 'facilitating environment' at an institutional level (Sambunjak and Marusic, 2009). This has resulted in a lack of clarity of mentor/mentee roles (Nakanjako, 2011; Ssemata et al., 2017). Therefore, mentoring approaches and guidelines geared towards the Global North are not always suited to the infrastructure and culture of African countries (Lescano et al., 2019; Hansoti et al., 2019; Ssemata et al., 2017).

This research has highlighted some of the stronger 'sponsorship' elements of mentoring in Africa, including a strong overlap between mentoring and supervision (Lescano et al., 2019; Ssemata et al., 2017; Somefun and Adebayo, 2019) – for example, Megginson and Clutterbuck (2005) noted that senior academics in South Africa were often asked to perform both a supervisor and mentor role, meaning that hierarchy and feedback on work impacted the openness and trust of the mentoring relationship (p.98). Also, academic writing is often included as a component of mentoring and it is common for writing training (Chi et al., 2019), tutoring and thesis advising (Lescano et al., 2019) to be referred to as mentoring. Mentoring is often evaluated on proposal writing and research publication outcomes (Nwankwo, 2017; Ngongalah et al., 2021). Additionally, African researchers lack the same access to research networks as their Global North contemporaries, so the role of mentors in networking support is crucial (Chi, et al., 2019). However, mentees also appreciate psychosocial support and empathy (Somefun and Adebayo, 2019), and appreciate a 'safe' environment to freely express concerns (Ngongalah, Rawlings et al., 2021).

The African cultural context

So does this mean that mentoring in Africa is more strongly oriented towards a 'sponsorship' model? When considering different cultures and organisational goals, it's clear that sponsorship and developmental mentoring may exist on a spectrum (Clutterbuck, 2007, p.652), but scant research has been done which investigates the societal and cultural influences on mentoring (Sambunjak et al., 2006). Even fewer studies have considered this through an African lens, with an exception being Sawatsky et al., (2016)'s qualitative study and thematic analysis in Malawi that identified intrapersonal, interpersonal and institutional factors that affect the mentoring relationship.

African philosophical concepts such as Ubuntu might provide an additional insight into the complexities of mentoring in the African culture (Geber and Keane, 2017; Mulaudzi et al., 2009; Tsotetsi and Omodan, 2020). Ubuntu principles potentially align with sponsorship models – for example hierarchy and respect for elders as a norm (Geber and Keane, 2017) – which can potentially create a sharp division between personal and professional boundaries (Sawasky et al., 2016). The principle of 'inclusion' should influence mentors towards proactive sponsorship, affirming, and socialising (Mulaudzi et al., 2009; Geber and Keane, 2017). Interdependence with community is also key in Ubuntu and success as a collective effort rather than a solo heroic event (Tsotetsi and Omodan, 2020), in contrast with individualist cultures that stress the mentee is responsible for their own learning (Clutterbuck, 2007), which suggests a more mentor-led relationship. On the other hand, the sharing of

stories in Ubuntu mentoring allows for vulnerability as a way of building trust (Hinsdale, 2016), and resonates more with a person-to-person psychotherapeutic model (Clarkson, 1995, p.20). Additionally it also suggests a more equitable, balanced dialogue space built on mutual trust and respect for the mentee's "way of knowing" (Tsoetsi and Omodan, 2020; Malatji et al., 2015). Despite this growing theoretical base, there is little to no research or case studies using these frameworks to analyse mentoring in the African context.

Conclusion

Academic mentoring covers many bases on the development/sponsorship spectrum, and it's unclear whether African academic mentoring maps onto this theoretical lens in practice, or if there are more nuanced, culturally relevant frameworks to explain the African context. Further qualitative research is needed to understand expectations and lived experience of mentoring by African researchers across different disciplines and contexts, which will be of interest to theorists, practitioners and policymakers.

References

- Adedokun, B., Nyasulu, P., Maseko, F., Adedini, S., Akinyemi, J., Afolabi, S., de Wet, N., Sulaimon, A., Sambai, C., Utembe, W., Opiyo, R., Awotidebe, T., Chirwa, E., Nabakwe, E., Niragire, F., Uwizeye, D., Niwemahoro, C., Kamndaya, M., Mwakalinga, V., Otwombe, K., 2014. Sharing perspectives and experiences of doctoral fellows in the first cohort of Consortium for Advanced Research Training in Africa: 2011–2014. *Global Health Action* 7, 25127. <https://doi.org/10.3402/gha.v7.25127>
- Ameh, P. o, McGuire, C.M., Waes, A. van, Fatusin, B.B., MacIntyre, L.S., Lelei-Mailu, F., Kodicherla, H., Buadu, M.A.E., Dankyau, M., Yakubu, K., 2022. Research activity, facilitators and barriers amongst trainee and early-career family physicians in sub-Saharan Africa: A cross-sectional survey. *African Journal of Primary Health Care & Family Medicine* 14, 10.
- Bennett, S., Paina, L., Ssengooba, F., Waswa, D., M'Imunya, J.M., 2013. Mentorship in African health research training programs: an exploratory study of fogarty international center programs in Kenya and Uganda. *Education for Health* 26, 183. <https://doi.org/10.4103/1357-6283.126001>
- Bozeman, B., Feeney, M.K., 2007. Toward a Useful Theory of Mentoring: A Conceptual Analysis and Critique. *Administration & Society* 39, 719–739. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0095399707304119>
- Brown, R.T., Daly, B.P., Leong, F.T.L., 2009. Mentoring in research: A developmental approach. *Professional Psychology: Research and Practice* 40, 306–313. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0011996>
- Carroll, M.A., Barnes, E.F., 2015. Strategies for Enhancing Diverse Mentoring Relationships in STEM Fields. *International Journal of Evidence Based Coaching and Mentoring* 13, 58–69.
- Chan, A.W., Yeh, C.J., Krumboltz, J.D., 2015. Mentoring ethnic minority counseling and clinical psychology students: A multicultural, ecological, and relational model. *J Couns Psychol* 62, 592–607. <https://doi.org/10.1037/cou0000079>
- Chi, B.H., Belizan, J.M., Blas, M.M., Chuang, A., Wilson, M.D., Chibwasha, C.J., Farquhar, C., Cohen, C.R., Raj, T., 2019. Evaluating Academic Mentorship Programs in Low- and Middle-Income Country Institutions: Proposed Framework and Metrics. *Am J Trop Med Hyg* 100, 36–41. <https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.18-0561>
- Chitsamatanga, B.B., Rembe, S., Shumba, J., 2018. Mentoring for Female Academics in the 21st Century: A Case Study of a South African University. *IJGWS* 6. <https://doi.org/10.15640/ijgws.v6n1a5>
- Clutterbuck, D., 2014. *Everyone needs a mentor*. CIPD.
- Clutterbuck, D., 2007. An International Perspective on Mentoring, in: Ragins, B.R., Kram, K.E. (Eds.), *The Handbook of Mentoring at Work: Theory, Research, and Practice*. SAGE Publications, Incorporated, Thousand Oaks, UNITED STATES.
- Cole, D.C., Johnson, N., Mejia, R., McCullough, H., Turcotte-Tremblay, A.-M.,

- Barnoya, J., Falabella Luco, (María) Soledad, 2016. Mentoring health researchers globally: Diverse experiences, programmes, challenges and responses. *Global Public Health* 11, 1093–1108. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17441692.2015.1057091>
- Collins, A., Lewis, I., Stracke, E., Vanderheide, R., 2014. Talking career across disciplines: Peer group mentoring for women academics. *International Journal of Evidence Based Coaching and Mentoring* 12, 92–108.
- Etzkorn, K.B., Braddock, A., 2020. Are you my mentor? A study of faculty mentoring relationships in US higher education and the implications for tenure. *International Journal of Mentoring and Coaching in Education* 9, 221–237. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJMCE-08-2019-0083>
- Gandhi, M., Raj, T., Fernandez, R., Rispel, L., Nxumalo, N., Lescano, A.G., Bukusi, E.A., Mmbaga, B.T., Heimburger, D.C., Cohen, C.R., 2019. Mentoring the Mentors: Implementation and Evaluation of Four Fogarty-Sponsored Mentoring Training Workshops in Low-and Middle-Income Countries. *Am J Trop Med Hyg* 100, 20–28. <https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.18-0559>
- Garvey, B., 2018. Mentoring in a coaching world, in: Cox, E., Bachkirova, T., Clutterbuck, D. (Eds.), *The Complete Handbook of Coaching*. SAGE, Los Angeles.
- Geber, H., Keane, M., 2013. Extending the worldview of coaching research and practice in Southern Africa: the concept of Ubuntu. *International Journal of Evidence Based Coaching and Mentoring* 11, 8–18.
- Hansoti, B., Kalbarczyk, A., Hosseinipour, M.C., Prabhakaran, D., Tucker, J.D., Nachega, J., Wallis, L., Stiles, J.K., Wynn, A., Morroni, C., 2019. Global Health Mentoring Toolkits: A Scoping Review Relevant for Low- and Middle-Income Country Institutions. *Am J Trop Med Hyg* 100, 48–53. <https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.18-0563>
- Hinsdale, M.J., 2016. Mentoring and Decolonization, in: Peters, M.A. (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of Educational Philosophy and Theory*. Springer Singapore, Singapore, pp. 1–7. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-287-532-7_511-1
- Jackson, V.A., Palepu, A., Szalacha, L., Caswell, C., Carr, P.L., Inui, T., 2003. “Having the Right Chemistry”: A Qualitative Study of Mentoring in Academic Medicine. *Academic Medicine* 78, 328–334.
- Jenkins, L.S., Makwero, M., Ameh, P., Motlathledi, K., Ayisi, -Boateng Nana K., McGuire, C.M., Fatusin, B.B., Yakubu, K., 2020. Exploring gaps, strategies and solutions for primary care research mentorship in the African context : a workshop report. *African Journal of Primary Health Care and Family Medicine* 12, 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.4102/phcfm.v12i1.2320>
- Kashiwagi, D.T., Varkey, P., Cook, D.A., 2013. Mentoring Programs for Physicians in Academic Medicine: A Systematic Review. *Academic Medicine* 88, 1029–1037. <https://doi.org/10.1097/ACM.0b013e318294f368>
- Katz, F., Glass, R.I., 2019. Mentorship Training is Essential to Advancing Global Health Research. *The American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene* 100, 1–2. <https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.18-0694>
- Lancer, N., Clutterbuck, D., Megginson, D., 2016. *Techniques for Coaching*

and Mentoring. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315691251>

Lescano, A.G., Cohen, C.R., Raj, T., Rispel, L., Garcia, P.J., Zunt, J.R., Hamer, D.H., Heimbürger, D.C., Chi, B.H., Ko, A.I., Bukusi, E.A., 2019a. Strengthening Mentoring in Low- and Middle-Income Countries to Advance Global Health Research: An Overview. *Am J Trop Med Hyg* 100, 3–8. <https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.18-0556>

Megginson, D., Clutterbuck, D., 1995. *Mentoring in action: a practical guide for managers*. Kogan Page, London.

Merriam, S., 1983. Mentors and Protégés: A Critical Review of the Literature. *Adult Education* 33, 161–173. <https://doi.org/10.1177/074171368303300304>

Mulaudzi, F.M., Libster, M.M., Phiri, S., 2009. Suggestions for Creating a Welcoming Nursing Community: Ubuntu, Cultural Diplomacy, and Mentoring. *Int J Hum Caring* 13, 45–51. <https://doi.org/10.20467/1091-5710.13.2.45>

Mullen, C.A., Klimaitis, C.C., 2021. Defining mentoring: a literature review of issues, types, and applications. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences* 1483, 19–35. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nyas.14176>

Nakanjako, D., Byakika-Kibwika, P., Kintu, K., Aizire, J., Nakwagala, F., Luzige, S., Namisi, C., Mayanja-Kizza, H., Kanya, M.R., 2011. Mentorship needs at academic institutions in resource-limited settings: a survey at makerere university college of health sciences. *BMC Medical Education* 11, 53. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6920-11-53>

Nakanjako, D., Katamba, A., Kaye, D.K., Okello, E., Kanya, M.R., Sewankambo, N., Mayanja-Kizza, H., 2014. Doctoral training in Uganda: evaluation of mentoring best practices at Makerere university college of health sciences. *BMC Medical Education* 14, 9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6920-14-9>

Nangami, M.N., Rugema, L., Tebeje, B., Mukose, A., 2014. Institutional capacity for health systems research in East and Central Africa schools of public health: enhancing capacity to design and implement teaching programs. *Health Research Policy and Systems* 12, 22. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1478-4505-12-22>

Nganga, C., Bowne, M., Stremmel, A., 2020. Mentoring as a developmental identity process. *Mentoring & Tutoring: Partnership in Learning* 28, 259–277. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13611267.2020.1783498>

Ngongalah, L., Rawlings, N.N., Musisi, J., Awanchiri, K., Akwah, E., Ngeh, E., Ssemwanga, A., 2021b. Mentorship as a strategy to improve research ability of students and young researchers in Africa: an exploratory study and initial findings on the CORE Africa Research Mentorship Scheme (preprint). *Scientific Communication and Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.01.29.428492>

Nwankwo, T.V., Ike, C.P., Anozie, C.O., 2017. Mentoring of young librarians in South East Nigeria for improved research and scholarly publications. *Library Management* 38, 455–476. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LM-11-2016-0083>

Okurame, D.E., 2008. Mentoring in the Nigerian academia: experiences and challenges. *International Journal of Evidence Based Coaching and Mentoring*

6, 45–56.

Oppong, E., Bao, H., Tang, W., Echavarria Mejia, M.I., Glozah, F., Asanga, N., Boinett, C.J., Aguilar, A.M., Valido, E., Lestari, T., Tucker, J.D., 2022. A Global Crowdsourcing Open Call to Improve Research Mentorship in Low- and Middle-Income Countries: A Mixed Methods Analysis. *The American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene* 106, 250–256. <https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.21-0607>

Owusu-Agyeman, Y., 2022. The Mentoring Experiences of Early Career and Senior Academics in a Multicampus University in South Africa. *EDUPIJ* 11. <https://doi.org/10.22521/edupij.2022.111.5>

Phiri, L.L., 2019. Mentee perceptions of beneficence of faculty-centered academic mentoring: Reflections from a pilot program. *South African Journal of Higher Education* 33, 265–282. <https://doi.org/10.20853/33-6-3007>

Revelo, R.A., Loui, M.C., 2016. A Developmental Model of Research Mentoring. *College Teaching* 64, 119–129. <https://doi.org/10.1080/87567555.2015.1125839>

Rheineck, J., Roland, C., 2011. The Developmental Mentoring Relationship Between Academic Women - Rheineck - 2008 - *Adultspan Journal* <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/j.2161-0029.2008.tb00048.x>

Rodríguez, D.C., Jessani, N.S., Zunt, J., Ardila-Gómez, S., Muwanguzi, P.A., Atanga, S.N., Sunguya, B., Farquhar, C., Nasuuna, E., 2021. Experiential Learning and Mentorship in Global Health Leadership Programs: Capturing Lessons from Across the Globe. *Annals of Global Health* 87, 61. <https://doi.org/10.5334/aogh.3194>

Rosser, E., Buckner, E., Avedissian, T., Cheung, D. s. k., Eviza, K., Hafsteinsdóttir, T.B., Hsu, M. y., Kirshbaum, M.N., Lai, C., Ng, Y. c., Ramsbotham, J., Waweru, S., 2020. The Global Leadership Mentoring Community: building capacity across seven global regions. *International Nursing Review* 67, 484–494. <https://doi.org/10.1111/inr.12617>

Sambunjak, D., 2015. Understanding wider environmental influences on mentoring: Towards an ecological model of mentoring in academic medicine. *Acta Med Acad* 44, 47–57. <https://doi.org/10.5644/ama2006-124.126>

Sambunjak, D., Marušić, A., 2009. Mentoring: What's in a Name? *JAMA* 302, 2591. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2009.1858>

Sambunjak, D., Straus, S.E., Marusic, A., 2010. A Systematic Review of Qualitative Research on the Meaning and Characteristics of Mentoring in Academic Medicine. *J GEN INTERN MED* 25, 72–78. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11606-009-1165-8>

Sawatsky, Adam P., Parekh, N., Muula, A.S., Mbata, I., Bui, T., 2016. Cultural implications of mentoring in sub-Saharan Africa: a qualitative study. *Medical Education* 50, 657–669. <https://doi.org/10.1111/medu.12999>

Schriever, V., Grainger, P., 2019. Mentoring an early career researcher: insider perspectives from the mentee and mentor. *Reflective Practice* 20, 720–731. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14623943.2019.1674272>

Somefun, O.D., Adebayo, K.O., 2021. The role of mentoring in research ecosystems in Sub-Saharan Africa: Some experiences through the CARTA opportunity. *Global Public Health* 16, 36–47. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17441692.2020.1776365>

Ssemata, A.S., Gladding, S., John, C.C., Kiguli, S., 2017a. Developing mentorship in a resource-limited context: a qualitative research study of the experiences and perceptions of the makerere university student and faculty mentorship programme. *BMC Medical Education* 17, 123. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-017-0962-8>

T. Tsotetsi, C., Isaiiah Omodan, B., 2020. Deconstructing power differentials in the postgraduate supervision process : mentoring in Ubuntu praxis. *Ubuntu* 9, 105–126. <https://doi.org/10.31920/2050-4950/2020/9n1a6>

Zentgraf, L.L., 2020. Mentoring reality: from concepts and theory to real expertise and the mentor's point of view. *International Journal of Mentoring and Coaching in Education* 9, 427–443. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJMCE-12-2017-0077>